

Challenges In Health Administrations, Reducing Readmission and Improving Healthcare

Quality Improvement

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1.0 Introduction

For improved Healthcare administration in the face of advancing technology and escalating challenges, Hospitals are adopting Service-for-free payment model. This move obliterates facing communication and decision making impediments, ensure timely and accurate statistics are available to be used in decision making and formulation of policies and solving of other health care issues. Fee-for-service payment model has been used in the global healthcare industry; a payment model in which services and payment are delivered as a unit as opposed to bundling and tracking for quality or appropriateness of service. This reimbursement provides incentives for provision of quantity healthcare rather than quality. According to Irio, Bosco, Slover, Sayeed and Zuckerman (2017), this has resulted in health care cost inflationary rise and overutilization and therefore a decrease in quality healthcare delivery to patients. There is therefore need for testing the models of payment for healthcare reimbursement that have been used in the private sector, such as accountable care organizations ACO's, bundled health initiatives, patient-centred medical homes and hospital readmission fines whose main aim is to provide incentives for utilization of services and keep patients healthy and out of hospitals and emergency rooms (Peters, Klijn, Stronks&Harting, 2017).

This will ensure smooth decision making, easy communication and smooth accounting, provide statistics for decision making and help solve health issues. Many healthcare organizations are unprepared for this reimbursement shift and are still facing readmission fines. As a result of these annually cumulative fines, Public Healthcare providers are seeking solutions for provision of quality healthcare, readmission reduction and patient compliance to curb fines and penalties(Keasberry, Scott, Sullivan, Staib& Ashy, 2017).

This paper will be an analysis of the current challenges that administrations in healthcare organizations face in achieving reduced readmission and healthcare quality improvement and enhance Healthcare administration. This will encompass the analysis of obstacles, currently available interventions and tools and most effective specific strategies for public healthcare organizations (Sharma, Chandrasekaran, Boyer &McDermont, 2017).

2.0 Description of the problem

Healthcare organizations vary with locations. Despite this, most hospitals and provider networks face similar administration problems, though to different degrees, of funding, patient outreach and uncompensated healthcare provision(Irio, Bosco, Slover, Sayeed& Zuckerman, 2017). Most hospitals globally have a mission to provide quality healthcare and community benefit. St Mary's health-one of America's largest healthcare systems providing care to over one million outpatient visitors yearly, will be used as a case study. Its mission is to advocate, teach, care and serve vulnerable Marion County populations. Just like most hospitals, St. Mary's Heath accepts health insurance payment. By doing this, it provides emergency room services to patients without regard to payment abilities and partakes cost saving measures, fines and penalties. This implies that the hospital has to balance the high uncompensated care levels and maintaining sustainability as a business entity.

Hospitals are very sensitive to reimbursement fluctuations and this is reflected in the quality of care received and the economy of a region since hospitals are some of the biggest employers in a region(Nelson & Staggers, 2017). The passage of the Affordable Care Act and reimbursement strategies imply that hospitals have to provide quality care outside of the hospitals including patient care, patient education and engagement improvement and readmission reduction. This can be achieved by the use of integrated technology system and workflows to

enhance communication as opposed to the use of electronic medical records system used at St. Mary's hospital that make information transfer and patient follow-up difficult.

Irio, Bosco, Slover, Sayeed and Zuckerman (2017) argue that understanding and effective implementation of strategies for integration improvement and population health management promotion is crucial in order to accommodate the changing payment structures that will result in reimbursements decline in the quality and uncompensated care provision mission(Keasberry, Scott, Sullivan, Staib& Ashy, 2017). The adoption of these strategies is important to the mission and vision of the St. Mary's Hospital as well as to its business and economic viability maintenance.

3.0 Information and Literature Review

The impacts the 2008 recession pushed the St. Mary's Health to working on a limited budget and slight profit margins. Price fluctuations are potentially dangerous to hospitals, making it crucial to understand the future reimbursement changes and tools that can be used in the reimbursement receipt. A range of reimbursement issues affect the St. Mary's Hospital and others across the Marion County and the nation.

3.1 Readmission Penalties

Readmission penalties are one of the issues that hospitals face. According to the Affordable Care Act, hospitals with excess thirty day readmission face payment and penalties. Excess readmission ratio in comparison with the national average results in Medicare payment penalties(Keasberry, Scott, Sullivan, Staib& Ashy, 2017). These penalties have an adjustment depending on clinically relevant factors. Revised Medicare policies exempt physician-planned readmission from penalties. This revision though does not address such facts like readmissions being a result of social factors that affect patients and the community. Hospitals are increasingly

being fined for readmission nationally(Sloan & Hsieh, 2017). Those in rural and impoverished areas incur more admission penalties. Readmissions present a high threat to the St. Mary's Hospitals and others financially. Strategies and policies are required to solve readmission penalties.

3.2 Value-Based Purchasing

Value based purchasing in another crucial incentive program(Peters, Klijn, Stronks&Harting, 2017). This offers bonuses to hospitals with quality measures and adheres to clinical guidelines for appropriate delivery of care on patient satisfaction and experience, safety, mortality and spending. Hospitals that do notobserve the guidelines faceValue-Based Purchasing penalties.A high level of technology adoption is required within the St. Mary's Hospital to improve these quality metrics.

3.3 Uncompensated care

High levels of uncompensated care provided are a financial threat to the St. Mary's Health. This happens when hospitals provide free and discounted services to patients that need financial assistance and are unable to pay the whole or a portion of the services. This practice has a negative impact on the operation and profitability(Irio, Bosco, Slover, Sayeed& Zuckerman, 2017). St. Mary's Health is labelled a safety net hospital and so the burden is greater due to the fact that it provides uninsured and underinsured with services. Many safety net hospitals have shut down in the recent past due to the great financial strain they face. The high levels of the uninsured and underinsured without primary care access in Marion County pose great cash-flow problems to the St. Mary's Health, which is the largest in the region(Nelson & Staggers, 2017). They burden the available resources and time of the Hospital. To curb this, increased financial help from the government and donors should be appealed for

4.0 Description of the project

The mentioned challenges that St Mary's Health face are experienced by others across the Marion County and the nation. Several models can be employed to manage readmissions, improve quality and reduce uncompensated care burden. Improving patient engagement and care coordination improvement with specific focus on technology are the most viable to be applied in the St. Mary's Health.

4.1 Patient Engagement

This entails a set of interventions that improve patient attachment and commitment to their health. This is aimed at increasing patient knowledge about their health and diagnoses, embracing healthy behaviours and maintaining treatment regimens (Nelson & Staggers, 2017). Several interventions can be employed by the hospital, including educational material dissemination, community resource connection and peer support and case managers or nurse's appointment for patient recovery follow up. Technology can be employed to boost patient engagement. This can be achieved by the use of smart phones and computers. Standards will be increased through the use of patient portals, apps, text messaging and email reminders and phone calls from case managers (Sloan & Hsieh, 2017). This will help in putting information into actionable formats for patients.

4.2 Care Coordination

This will also help reduce readmissions, improve patient satisfaction and reduce uncompensated care burden (Peters, Klijn, Stronks & Harting, 2017). It is always linked to patient engagement, but different. The difference between the two terms is that care coordination concentrates on how healthcare organizations and providers build roadmaps for patients to follow whereas patient engagement is the patient encouragement process for using the roadmaps

provided. Care coordination is done by deliberately organizing care activities between two or more participants together with the patient to facilitate appropriate healthcare service delivery(Nelson & Staggers, 2017). This involves resource and personnel marshalling to carry out patient care activities. It is always managed by information exchange among participants.

Challenges to the employment of this model include that fact that it is difficult to implement on low costs. The coordinators also lack the time and capacity to follow up on individual patients for understanding of patient needs at different times and the effective intervention tools. Deployment of technology can help improve care coordination by reducing the information reception and remitting time, thereby reducing the turn-around time(Sharma, Chandrasekaran, Boyer &McDermont, 2017). This can also help improve data receipt verification and confirmation. St. Mary's Health, for instance, uses device vendor in sleep apnea monitoring. It creates records and faxes and numerous paperback sheets of patient everyday information not correctly categorized or received is lost. Cloud based system usage in data transmission will reduce time spent in data transmission and transfer safeguarding(Sloan & Hsieh, 2017).

5.0 Conclusion

Hospitals face tremendous administrative and financial pressure. Burdens of uninsured, reimbursement penalties and fines have placed the St. Mary's Hospital in a precarious situation(Irio, Bosco, Slover, Sayeed& Zuckerman, 2017). Integrated healthcare system and payment is a solution to quality and quality care provision improvement. Patient engagement and care coordination models are viable options for the implementation of these proposals. Healthcare organisations should therefore purchase education programs to ensure that employees are ell educated and informed of these contemporary healthcare problems and how their roles

relate to the operations that should be adopted to get the organisation onto a modern effective care provision platform.

The education and training of employees should also be done on technology. Technology is also a significant factor in a healthcare organization's viability. Technology is promising effective patient and caregiver connection and reduces readmissions and improves patient satisfaction(Keasberry, Scott, Sullivan, Staib& Ashy, 2017).These technologies will become a common service in such hospitals as St Mary's Health. Technology can be invested in long-term and short term benefit tracking in hospitals with limited resources. This will benefit both hospitals and patients.

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